

**Seed Production Protection and Certification under sui generis
legislation mandated by TRIPS agreement in India with Special
Reference to Kashmir Valley**

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ABSTRACT

Agriculture has remained the backbone of an economy and in need of legal protection. Seeds form an important outcome of agricultural process and technology has made a tremendous impact on production, process and propagation of seeds which needed legal intervention and hence PPVFR in India in the background of international consensus. However, has the law worked towards protection of seeds in an effective manner that needs to be probed into?

Seeds are the most important input the farmers rely upon for assumed yield. Seeds are the foundation of Agriculture. Seed symbolizes life as it paves the way for several varieties and crops for the benefit of Humans and the economy. Since most of the farming community is illiterate or semi-literate, it is the responsibility of the Government to frame rules that govern that production and distribution of quality seeds to the farming community.

This Paper shall analyze how seeds are formed and released as per their quality and practice. It shall also see how law and policy offers the protection.

Key Words: Breeder Seed, Multiplication of Seeds, TLS, PPVFR, Foundation Seed etc.

INTRODUCTION

Modern seed supply systems are primarily dependent on improved varieties which are developed by crop breeding programmes. The seeds of these candidate varieties are officially tested for yield, adaptability and resistance to biotic and abiotic stress in coordinated trials for at least three years. The promising varieties are identified in workshops of respective crop improvement projects.¹

The varieties are notified after their release for general cultivation by Central Sub-committee on Crop Standards, Release and Notification of Varieties. This committee takes into consideration the performance of a candidate variety in the trials under the All India Coordinated Research Improvement Project of a given crop in respect of yield, disease, and pest resistance, adaptability to specific climate conditions and other economically desirable characteristics. Only varieties superior to the existing ones in respect of desirable characters are released and notified. The varieties which perform better at state level are released in the state by State Variety Release Committee. However, notification of varieties is done only by Central Seed Committee after its approval by Central Sub-committee on Crop Standards, Release and Notification.²

1. SEED MULTIPLICATION SYSTEM

At the time of release of a variety, small quantity of seed, normally known as nucleus seed, is available with the plant breeder. Commercial quantity of seed is produced after a series of multiplication steps. Starting from maintenance programme in which nucleus seed is produced by the breeder or the sponsored breeder, the seed is multiplied in a generation system of breeder, foundation and certified seed. Each time a variety goes through the cycle of multiplication; there is a chance of its deterioration through mechanical admixture, pollination by alien pollen or mutations. The possibility of contamination by alien pollen is greater in cross-

¹ The Seed Testing Laboratory is located at **Division of Seed Science & Technology, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi**, has been notified as the Central Seed Testing Laboratory and it was established during 1960.30-Apr-2020

² Chopra V. L. (2004). Plant breeding theory and practice second edition. Oxford and IBH Publishing Com. Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi Calcutta.

pollinated species than in the self-fertilized ones. However, even in species classified as self-fertilizing, there can be small proportion of cross-fertilization³.

The longer the sequence of multiplication, the greater the possibility that one or a combination of factors may occur to erode the essential qualities of a cultivar. Across three generations the State and National Seeds Corporations have been supplying seeds for normal produce to the farms of progressive growers. This seed supplied to private seed companies and farmers for sowing leads to the commercialization and often affects the genetic purity of the gene. However, because of large sized breeder seed crop maintaining standards are not feasible especially when multiplied outside their 'area of origin', with differential response to photo-period and temperature in the new environment. Development and seed production of a set of genotypes, thus usually alter genetic composition of the new area. Though, growing seed for one generation in a different environment does not have a significant effect, but over generations the effect can be cumulative⁴.

These considerations have led to the generation system of seed multiplication which is based on number of generations the seed is removed from the maintenance programme. In this system the seed is multiplied through the following three classes:

2.1. Breeder Seed

Breeder seed is produced from nucleus seed under the supervision of a qualified plant breeder in a research institute/agricultural university. This provides initial seed source for recurring increase of foundation seed. Breeder seed is monitored by a joint inspection team of scientists and officials of Seed Certification Agency and National or State Seed Corporation.⁵

2.2. Foundation Seed

Foundation seed is the progeny of breeder seed. Foundation seed can also be produced from breeder seed particularly in crops like groundnut where seed multiplication ratio is low. This class of seed is known as foundation seed stage-I

³ Smith and Whittington (1991) reported that out pollination in wheat occurs with a frequency of 4% and Bickelmann (1993) found 1.1 to 8.7% of out crossing in oats.

⁴ Prasad, G. S., Rao, C. S., Suneetha, K., Muralidharan, K., & Siddiq, E. A. (2022). Impact of breeder seed multiplication and certified quality seed distribution on rice production in India. *CABI Agriculture and Bioscience*, 3(1), 1-22.

⁵ Kumar, N., & Singh, M. (2019). Production and maintenance of nucleus and breeder's seed. *Annals of Horticulture*, 12(1), 88-92.

and it can be clearly traced to breeder seed. This is also known as certified foundation seed since its production is supervised and approved by the certification agency.⁶ Foundation seed is produced by State Agricultural Universities, state farm corporation of India, National seeds Corporation, state Seed corporations or some of the leading private seed companies under the technical officers. Foundation seed is known as basic seed in certain countries under organization for Economic co-operation and development (OECD)⁷ seed Certifications schemes.⁸ The OECD Guidelines for Multinational Enterprises (OECD Guidelines) are recommendations from governments to multinational enterprises on responsible business conduct. The OECD Guidelines set standards for responsible business conduct across a range of issues such as human rights, labour rights, and the environment.⁹

2.3. Certified Seed

Certified seed is the progeny of foundation seed and its production is supervised and approved. Its reproduction does not exceed three generations beyond foundation seed stage 1. The seed of this class is normally produced by the State and National Seeds Corporations and private seed companies on the farms of progressive growers. The seed is the commercial seed which is visible to the farmers for sowing.¹⁰

In the generation system of seed multiplication, the genetic purity of breeder seed crop is maintained at 100%. However, because of large sized multiplication plots, strict genetic purity standards are not feasible in practice at foundation and certified seed production stages. Therefore, as per minimum seed certification standards, the maximum permissible off types in rice, wheat and sorghum are as follows.

⁶ Foundation seed (or Basic seed): Foundation seed, also known as basic seed, is the descendent of breeder seed and is produced under conditions that ensure maintaining genetic purity and identity. 13-Mar-2020 available at : <https://www.agrilinks.org/post/seed-system-definitions>

⁷ The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) is a unique forum where the governments of 37 democracies with market-based economies collaborate to develop policy standards to promote sustainable economic growth.

⁸ Jason Nickerson, Seed System Definitions, , March 13, 2020 available at : <https://www.agrilinks.org/post/> ; see also *OECD Seed Scheme Rules, Regulations and Guidelines*, it contains the 2022 edition of the *Rules and Regulations* of the *OECD Seed Schemes* paving way for global approach to seed industry.

⁹ The OECD Guidelines, available at : <https://www.oecdwatch.org/oecd-ncps/>

¹⁰ The OECD Schemes for the Varietal Certification of Seed, established in 1958, promotes the use of certified agriculture seed that is of consistently high quality. These seeds are produced – and officially controlled – according to a set of harmonized procedures put in place in the 61 participating countries.

Crop	Max. permissible off-type in	Certified
	Foundation %	
Rice & Wheat	0.05	0.20
Sorghum (hybrid)	0.05	0.10

Similarly, for other crops variable frequencies of off types are allowed in the foundation and certified seed production plots. Standards for germination, physical purity and seed health are practically similar for foundation and carried seed classes. However, they differ with regards to genetic purity, which is slightly lower in the latter class. India is trying to maintain its trust with standardizing the quality and purity of the seeds compatible with international certification level which was materialized in the latest endeavors in this regard both at national as well as regional level¹¹.

2.4. Truthfully Labeled Seed (TLS)

One more class of seeds is truthfully labeled seed. This type of seeds does not come under the purview of the Department of Seed Certification. This kind of seeds is tested only for its physical purity and germination. By this method, any farmer can produce seeds and market it as truthfully labeled seeds. Labeling is compulsory but certification is voluntary.¹²

2. SEED QUALITY CONTROL

Seed quality in India is legally controlled by the Seeds Act, 1966¹³. According to this Act all seeds of notified varieties/kinds sold to farmers must meet the minimum standards of germination and physical purity¹⁴. The seed should be packed in a suitable container and a label has to be affixed on the container. Information about

¹¹ The seed testing lab established by the Telangana State Seed and Organic Certification Authority (TSSOCA) with the nomenclature of Telangana International Seed Testing Authority (TISTA) at Rajendranagar here has secured the recognition of the International Seed Testing Authority (ISTA). The Hindu, Feb.10, 2022.

¹² See supra note 2

¹³ The main features of the Seeds Act, 1966 are: It is applicable only to notified kinds/varieties of seed and vegetatively propagating materials used for sowing. 2.it provides for the formation of an apex advisory body, namely, the Central Seed Committee; the Central seed Certification Board; establishment of Seed Certification Agencies; and Central and State Seed Testing Laboratories, etc.

¹⁴ The responsibilities for enforcing various provisions regarding regulation of sale of seeds of notified kinds/ varieties rest with the seed inspectors. The seed inspector is required to inspect of frequently as may be required all places used for the growing, storage or sale of any seed of any notified kind r variety; Satisfy himself that the conditions of the certificates/labels are being observed;

germination, physical purity, variety, date of test, name of the seed producer has to be given on the label. The germination as given on the label is valid for nine months from the test date, after which it has to be revalidated for a subsequent period of six months after re-test.¹⁵

3. SEED CERTIFICATION: PURPOSE OF SEED CERTIFICATION

The purpose of seed certification is to maintain and make available to farmers high quality seeds and propagating materials "of notified kind and varieties so grown and handled as to ensure cultivar identity and purity. Seed certification is also designed to achieve prescribed standards of seed germination, physical purity and seed borne diseases.¹⁶

Ideally in a seed production programme, the goal is to achieve 100 per cent genetic and physical purity, germination and complete freedom from diseases and pests. In practice, due to environmental, biological and human factors, this goal is seldom realized. Hence minimum standards are fixed for each quality attribute which is generally achievable in a given set of conditions of a country. Receipt and scrutiny of application from seed producer for certification of a seed production plot, Verification of seed source through checking of certification tag, seed container, purchase records etc. of the seed to be used for multiplication. It requires land requirement to ensure that land to be used for seed production is free of volunteer plant with prescribed isolation distance.¹⁷

4. Seeds Bill 2004: Salient Features & Current Status

According to a report published in Economic Times (February 13, 2017), the government is planning to revive the Seeds Bill, which was first introduced in 2004

¹⁵ A variety of seed containing any technology considered harmful or potentially harmful to environment and ecology shall not be registered. These transgenic seeds can only be registered after the applicant has obtained clearance from Environment (protection) Act, 1986. Every seed producer and dealer, and horticulture nursery has to be registered with state government. The Seed bill 2004 proposed to establish Central Seed Committee and sub-committees. Any type of seed which is for sale has to be registered with Registration sub-committee. The registration is valid 18 years for long duration perennial crops and for 15 years for annual/biennial crops. All registered seed has to meet the minimum standard with respect to the proportion of seed that must germinate, the level of physical and genetic purity and the permitted proportion of diseased seeds.

¹⁶ Phases of seed certification: Receipt and scrutiny of application. Verification of seed source. Field inspection. Post-harvest supervision of seed crops.; Seed sampling and testing.; Labelling, tagging, sealing and grant of certificate.

¹⁷ Udit Joshi, et al, Seed certification: importance, steps involved and types of seeds, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343999374_Seed_certification_importance_steps_involved_and_types_of_seeds

and last in 2014 but has never seen the light of the day. This bill should be seen in the context of Seed Act 1966 and the Protection of Plant Varieties and Farmers' Rights Act, 2001 (PPVFR). PPVFR Act set up a framework to protect the intellectual property rights of breeder and on the other hand safeguarding the rights of farmers.¹⁸ Import of seed would be subject to Plant Quarantine order, 2003 or any corresponding order under Destructive Insect and Pest Act, 1914. Such seeds should also conform to the minimum standard mentioned above. The government can restrict export of seed if it feels food security of India is affected.¹⁹

The standing Committee of Parliament recommended that the Plant Protection of Varieties and Farmers Rights Act, 2001 be made fully operative before the Seeds Bill, 2004 is passed. The Seeds Bill should aim to strengthen the integrated growth of farmers and commercial seed systems, so that every farmer has access to high quality seed/planting material at the right time and place and at appropriate prices.

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The purpose of field inspection is to ascertain whether the seed crop conforms to the minimum standards of genetic purity, health, and incidence. Broadly field inspection involves first to check if the plants of a seed crop conform to the description of the cultivar at that stage of growth.

5. STRUCTURE OF INDIAN SEED INDUSTRY AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

India is endowed with varied agro-climatic conditions suitable for the production of a wide variety of seeds. Coupled with expertise in major areas of seed production, quality control and evaluation, an advanced system of variety development, testing and release and a network of seed producing and certification agencies, our country has a tremendous potential for meeting the increasing demand for quality seed but also to emerge as a major force in the global seed market. The seed sector has made impressive strides over the last three decades. From a modest beginning of 465 hectares under seed production in 1962-63, the country today has an area of nearly 5 lakh hectares under certified seed production. Similarly, the quantum of

¹⁸ The bill was revived in 2014 after a decade but was again put on hold in 2015 after the backlash against the provisions relating to genetically modified (GM) seeds. This bill if passed has the potential to boost the agricultural growth. Recently NITI Aayog advocated for massive research in the field of improving seeds varieties including GM ones.

¹⁹ The penalty for contravening any provision of the Act or selling misbranded or substandard seeds is a fine ranging between Rs 25,000 and Rs 1 lakh. The penalty for giving false information may incur a prison term for up to a year and/or a fine of up to Rs 5 lakh.

²⁰ Standing Committee Report Summary, The Seeds Bill, 2004, PRS Legislative Report

quality seed distribution has increased from 14 lakh quintals in 1979-80 to 75.60 lakh quintals in 1997-98.²¹

The COVID-19 pandemic affected the seed industry, with the availability of quality seeds being the greatest challenge for farmers. The pandemic and the restrictions imposed by governments restricted the production, certification, and international trade of seeds, with serious consequences for farmers. Despite the various restrictions in the turnover of the seeds industry for 2021, vegetable seeds contributed the most with a 30% share, followed by cotton with about 18%, maize with 13%, and paddy with 10%.

There has been an increase in hybrid seed penetration in multiple crops in order to address the increasing food demand-supply gap in the country. Due to stagnant growth observed in the arable land and a constantly growing population, the per capita arable land has been declining. These factors, along with poor crop productivity, are likely to lead to pressure on the food supply in the country. In India, hybrid seed penetration is high in cotton (90%), corn (60%), limited cereals, such as sorghum and pearl millet, and oilseeds, such as sunflower (hybridization 80%). However, penetration is still very low in major cereals, such as paddy and wheat (5%). Cotton hybridization is almost reaching saturation, as BT cotton is sown in over 90% of the cotton-producing area in the country. Hybridization in corn, paddy, and vegetables is estimated to drive the sector's growth during the forecast period. The patenting process in India is not very vigorous, enabling companies to replicate better-performing seeds in the marketplace. In addition, after the discovery of a successful hybrid, seed multiplication needs many rounds of sowing. Therefore, the increasing government initiatives and investments by players are expected to drive the market in the country during the forecast period.²²

Research Institutes and Project Directorates of Indian Council of Agricultural Research and State Agricultural Universities are primarily responsible for the production of breeder seed. The foundation certified seed is produced by State Seed Corporations, National Seed Corporation, and State Farms Corporation of India and

²¹ India Seed Market - Growth, Trends, COVID-19 Impact, and Forecasts (2022 - 2027) ; The Indian seed market is projected to record a CAGR of 6.8% during the forecast period 2022-2027.

²² The seed sector in the country comprises of two national level Seed Corporations, i.e., National Seed Corporation and State Farm Corporation of India, 13 State Seed Corporations and more than 200 prominent private seed companies. For quality control and certification, there are 19 State Seed Certification Agencies and 96 State Seed Testing Laboratories.

private seed companies²³. This clearly brings out the potential which exists for levels of awareness among farmers about the importance of quality seeds and streamlining of the system for production and distribution of the seeds are necessary if this potential is to be realized. In addition, significant opportunities have also opened up for export of seeds of several varieties of crops for which India has a comparative advantage.²⁴

The permission for FDI up to 100% would encourage infusion of foreign investment into the seed sector and would also facilitate indigenous seed companies for strengthening of Research and Development activities for development of Seeds of better varieties. Government of India had initially introduced the New Policy on Seed Development in October, 1988 with the objective of making the planting material available anywhere in the world to Indian farmers for increasing productivity and production. The policy provided for liberal imports (subject to certain parameters and regulations) to achieve this objective as well as to encourage the growth of exports in seeds. Important changes in the national and international economic environment have taken place since the announcement of the Seed Policy of 1988. Investment in the seed sector has been considerably liberalized. While the change in policy in 1987 facilitated investment in the MRTP, FERA companies, the new industrial policy of 1991 identified investment in the seed sector as a high priority area in which foreign equity participation would be encouraged. India has also signed the GATT Treaty on Agriculture which is expected to give a boost to trade in agricultural commodities with significant export opportunities for developing countries. By acceding to the Agreement on Trade Related Intellectual Property Right (TRIPs), India is required to enact legislation for plant variety protection²⁵.

As per World Seed Trade Statistics, India has sixth largest size of domestic seed market in the world, estimated to be at about 1300 million dollars. However, India's share in global trade in seeds (import

²³ Though the Private sector has started to play a significant role in the production and distribution of seeds, particularly in the last decade, the organized seed sector for food crops continues to be dominated by public sector. This sector accounts only for about 7 to 10% of the total seed distributed in the country in the major food crops viz. wheat and rice. The production of the unorganized sector and the use of saved seed by farmers accounts for the other about 90%.

²⁴ As per extant policy, FDI is permitted up to 100% under the automatic route in development and production of seeds and planting material subject to certain conditions as mentioned in "Circular No. 1 of 2011: Consolidated FDI Policy" issued by Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion, Ministry of Commerce & Industry, Government of India. The permission for FDI up to 100% would encourage infusion of foreign investment into the seed sector and would also facilitate indigenous seed companies for strengthening of Research and Development activities for development of Seeds of better varieties.

²⁵ India enacted the Protection of Plant Variety and Farmers Act 2001 to fulfil the obligation TRIPs Agreement.

& export) is of only about 37 million dollars. To give a boost to seed export, India has decided to participate in OECD Seed Schemes for the following categories of crops: Grasses and legumes; Crucifers and other oil or fibre species; Cereals; Maize and sorghum; Vegetables.²⁶ The Scheme authorizes use of labels and certificates for seed produced and processed for international trade according to agreed principles²⁷. The department is in the process of completing other formalities under the OECD Seed Scheme guidelines before the certification work gets started.

6. Intellectual Property Rights and Seed Protection

It is widely accepted that "Plant variety Protection" (PVP), which grants Intellectual Property Rights" (IPR) to eligible plant varieties is essential to increase the availability of good quality seed of improved varieties. Breeding for high yielding varieties with all other desired characteristics requires considerable investments in trained staff and the allocation of funds. If PVP is not granted, the private seed sector will not be willing to invest in plant breeding. At the same time, the availability of seed of improved and protected varieties at low prices in NENA and ECO countries and the granting of farmers' rights as defined in the FAO fora are issues to be considered when establishing PVP laws.²⁸ The agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS) is one of the outcomes of the Uruguay Round Agreements under the World Trade Organization (WTO). The TRIPS Agreement was established on January 1, 1995 and is considered the most remarkable multilateral agreement on intellectual property. In regard to plants, the TRIPS Agreement addresses issues related to intellectual property protection of plant varieties, requiring protection either by patents or by a sui generis effective system or by a combination of both.

Most countries of the region have laws, which require that varieties should be registered to be released for commercialization. However, many countries do not have legislation for PVP²⁹.

²⁶ OECD Seed Schemes is one of the international frameworks available for certification of agricultural seeds moving in international trade. The objective of the OECD Seed Schemes is to encourage use of seeds of consistently high quality in participating countries.

²⁷ The Joint Secretary (Seeds) in the Department of Agriculture & Cooperation has been nominated as the National Designated Authority. Further, Heads of Seed Certification Agencies in Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Uttaranchal, Uttar Pradesh Haryana, Bihar and Assam have been nominated as the Designated Authorities under the Scheme to undertake certification work under OECD Seed Schemes.

²⁸ Turner, M. and Muminjanov, H. 2020. *A strategy for coordinated development of the seed sector in countries of the Economic Cooperation Organization region*. Rome, FAO.

²⁹ In Cyprus, Egypt, Ethiopia, Lebanon, Morocco, Oman, Syria and Tunisia, registration of varieties for commercial release is carried out through an independent body, for the evaluation of varieties according to the requirements established by the UPOV Convention, i.e., that is Distinctness, Uniformity and Stability (DUS).

Major breeding programmes have been carried out by government employees working in national research institutions or universities that did not seek any reward for their newly developed varieties. The great majority of seed (90%) is produced by the informal system, which makes it difficult to exercise Plant Breeders Rights. Local land varieties of the major cereal and legume crops whose breeders are unknown and, which are not eligible for PVP, are still grown³⁰. Several international organizations deal with plant variety protection and grant Plant Breeder's Rights. These organizations include the International Union for the protection of New Varieties of Plants (UPOV), which is an independent intergovernmental organization working in close collaboration with the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), and the International Association of Plant Breeders for the Protection of Plant Varieties (ASSINSEL).

As the Agreement does not define what would be considered a sui generis effective system, it will be for the TRIPS Council to Judge. Developing member countries are given longer Periods than other countries to develop their IPR legislation in compliance with the TRIPS Agreement (article 65-4).³¹ For plant breeding, intellectual property provisions are relevant not only to the product of plant breeding activity but also to the material that is involved in the development of varieties. For this reason, plant genetic resources are at the heart of the debate on consequences of the application of IPR principles. While seed companies in the private sector are pressing for early and wide spread application of IPR, gene rich developing countries perceive this as a threat from the technologically advanced private sector. It is feared that the wealth of the poor women and men who have conserved, preserved and enhanced biodiversity for centuries will be unethically appropriated³².

The TRIPS Agreement also defines in detail national civil and criminal procedures by which the rights of breeders are to be enforced. For example, it states that

³⁰ At a Plant Variety Protection workshop held in Cairo in 1999, it was indicated that many countries of the region are initiating procedures to develop legislation for the protection of Breeders' Rights.

³¹ Article 7 of the TRIPS Agreement, entitled Objectives, states: "the protection and enforcement of intellectual property rights should contribute to the technological innovation and to the transfer and dissemination of technology, to the mutual advantage of producers and users of technological knowledge and in a manner conducive to social and economic welfare and to a balance of rights and obligations.

³² Available at : https://www.researchgate.net/publication/350325482_Plant_genetic_resources_for_food_and_agriculture_for_sustainable_development/

procedures must be fair and equitable, not unnecessarily complicated or costly, and should avoid time limits or unwarranted delays. The TRIPS agreement does not intend to restrict trade, but to encourage it in balance with the promotion of technological innovations. Due to the benefits derived from protected varieties, it is believed that protected varieties are likely to be well maintained and continue to produce quality seed that is representative of the original variety. As a result, farmers will have confidence in the genetic properties of the varieties, which could have a positive effect on the national, regional, and global seed trade. However, protected material is expected to cost more because of the royalties that have to be paid to the breeder. Seed companies that incurred large expenses on developing varieties sought returns on their investments through legal means of regulating seed multiplication and sale. Ownership of plant varieties was protected by their developers and sale of seeds exclusively by the organization that developed the variety, or its licensee. Both ownership and sale were made a means of generating profit. Since legal ownership, and the protection it offered, as necessary to secure profits, different forms of protection to new crop varieties through systems of plant Breeder's rights (PBR) came into being.³³

7. Seeds Protection In J&K

JK Agri Genetic Limited (JKAGL) is a Leader in the research and development, production, processing and marketing of Bajra (Pearl Millet), Cotton, Jowar (Sorghum), Rice (Paddy), Mustard, Maize (Corn), Wheat and other Vegetable crops. The facility is managed by highly qualified, experiences, motivated and committed team of over eighty scientists working on a standard mandate in the company's strategically situated multiple breeding research centres and trial location centres that cover all the agro-climatic zones of India. The company has also been collaborating with several national and international institutes to develop distinguishable hybrids for customers. The company has well established in-house crop breeding and biotechnology R&D units recognised by the Department of Scientific and Industrial Research (DSIR), state-of-the-art biotechnology centre for Genomics and other new generation breeding tools. The world class infrastructure

³³ Amruta Desai and 2B.M Aher., seed legislations in India, www.ijcrt.org © 2017 IJCRT | Volume 5, Issue 4 December 2017 | ISSN: 2320-2882

supports 3 main research stations, 4 sub stations, 6 dynamic research stations, several multi location trial centres covering all agro-climatic zones in India. The use of BT cotton drastically reduced the amounts of chemical pesticides used on cotton. Our "X-Gene" Bt cotton technology is now commercially approved in Sudan, Ethiopia and Swaziland. It adheres to international quality control and quality assurance protocols to ensure best quality seeds to the farming community³⁴. It is estimated that the direct contribution of quality seed of a variety alone is about 15-20% to the total production. 1st important and feasible approach to enhance the productivity of any crop would be to produce quality seed and making it available to farmers at proper time. Several high yielding varieties with improved technologies have been developed by SKUAST-Kashmir from last three decades. There is urgent need to popularize these high yielding varieties amongst farmers so as to increase the productivity and production of various crops; keeping in view the alarming pace in the increase of population³⁵.

8. CONCLUSION

Seed is the basic and most critical input and acts as a delivery system through which all scientific advancements get transferred to crop production scenario as the efficiency of all agricultural inputs depends on quality seeds. India has slowly but steadily improved the production, distribution and propagation of seeds to boost its agriculture and horticulture sector. It has ratified not only the TRIPS Agreement related to agriculture but also adopted the OECD guidelines to improve the quality of seeds of agricultural products. J&K has undertaken various steps to improve the quality of seeds and plant varieties through active state intervention and research and development institutions established at various places besides the Agricultural Universities of Science and Technologies.

³⁴ Jkseeds ltd. available at: <https://www.jkagri.com/>

³⁵ Ilyas M.B. Ali G.Z.B. Seed manual. Special reference to description of varieties released by SKUST National Seed project (AICRP) S.K. University of Agriculture Science and technology of Kashmir,